

IF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS PREPARE PODCASTS: AN APPLICATION FOR LITERATURE COURSE**ÖĞRETMEN ADAYLARI PODCAST HAZIRLARSA: EDEBİYAT DERSİNE YÖNELİK BİR UYGULAMA****Ayşe Derya ESKİMEN**

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Abstract

The study involves pre-service teachers' producing content on Turkish literature authors and works through podcast application. Accordingly, the aim of the study is to address the attitudes of pre-service teachers who realized the podcast application towards collaborative work in literature course and their perceptions of information communication technologies competence. In addition, pre-service teachers' thoughts about preparing podcasts were also discussed. It is thought that the experience of such an application by pre-service teachers will contribute to the development of collaborative work, technology use and speaking skills. The study was conducted with thirty-six Turkish pre-service Turkish teachers in the spring semester of the 2021-2022 academic year within the scope of the new Turkish literature course 2. Quantitative and qualitative data collection methods were used in the study. The findings obtained as a result of the research are that pre-service teachers' perceptions of collaborative work towards preparing podcasts are at a "high" level; the mean scores of pre-service teachers' perceptions of ICT competence are at a "sufficient" level; there is no significant difference between their attitudes towards collaborative learning and their perceptions of competence in using ICT according to gender. The findings for the qualitative part are that the pre-service teachers enjoyed the study, their knowledge was reinforced with the preparations they made before the podcast on the subject they dealt with, and this provided permanence. They also stated that speaking and vocalizing, producing content was very satisfying, working with their friends was enjoyable, they learned new things about the use of technology through podcasts and saw their deficiencies.

Keywords: Turkish Language and Literature Education, Podcast, Verbal Communication**Öz**

Çalışma, öğretmen adaylarının podcast uygulaması yoluyla Türk edebiyatı yazar ve eserlerine yönelik içerik üretmelerini kapsamaktadır. Buna yönelik olarak araştırmada amaç, podcast uygulamasını gerçekleştiren öğretmen adaylarının; edebiyat dersinde işbirlikli çalışmaya yönelik tutumlarını ve bilgi iletişim teknolojileri yeterlik algılarını ele almaktır. Ayrıca öğretmen adaylarının podcast hazırlamaya yönelik düşünceleri de ele alınmıştır. Böyle bir uygulamanın öğretmen adaylarınca deneyimlenmesinin işbirlikli çalışma, teknoloji kullanımı ve konuşma becerilerini geliştirmeye yönelik katkılar sunacağı düşünülmektedir. Çalışma 2021-2022 eğitim öğretim yılı bahar döneminde yeni türk edebiyatı dersi 2 kapsamında otuz altı Türkçe öğretmen adayı ile gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırmada nicel ve nitel veri toplama yöntemleri kullanılmıştır. Araştırma sonucunda elde

edilen bulgular, öğretmen adaylarının podcast hazırlamaya yönelik işbirlikli çalışma algılarının “yüksek” düzeyde olduğu; öğretmen adayları için bilgi ve iletişim teknolojileri yeterlilik algısı puan ortalamalarının “yeterli” düzeyde olduğu; işbirlikli öğrenmeye yönelik tutumları ve bilgi iletişim teknolojileri kullanmaya ilişkin yeterlilik algıları arasında cinsiyete göre anlamlı bir fark olmadığı yönündedir. Nitel kısma yönelik bulgular öğretmen adaylarının çalışmadan zevk aldıkları, ele aldıkları konuya ilişkin podcast öncesi yaptıkları hazırlıklarla bilgilerinin pekiştiği ve bunun kalıcılık sağladığı yönündedir. Ayrıca konuşma ve seslendirmenin, içerik üretmenin oldukça tatmin edici olduğunu, arkadaşlarıyla birlikte çalışmanın zevk verdiğini podcast yoluyla teknoloji kullanımına ilişkin yeni şeyler öğrendiklerini ve eksiklerini gördüklerini ifade etmişlerdir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Türk Dili ve Edebiyatı Eğitimi, Podcast, Sözlü İletişim

Introduction

In the early twenty-first century, the emergence of Web 2.0 and the World Wide Web, which encourages collaboration and interaction, has had a significant impact on education. The implications for educators have been equally important, and teachers need to keep abreast of these developments and explore how they can help improve teaching and learning. The language skill areas of reading, writing, speaking and listening are today affected by developments such as digitalization and the use of Web 2.0 tools. Accordingly, a number of new applications have started to be used in digital environments for reading, listening, speaking and writing. There are applications such as wattpad, audio books, podcasts for these skill areas of language in digital environments. Podcast, one of these applications, is "Audio broadcasting was born from the combination of the words "iPod" meaning "portable music player" produced by Apple and "broadcast" meaning "broadcast" in English" (Brachet, 2007, 2). Podcasts are a series of digital audio recordings published on the web and pushed (or distributed) via a Rapid Simple Syndication (RSS feed) (Deal, 2007; King & Gura, 2007; Lafferty, & Walch, 2006 cited in Kim and King, 2011). The audio podcast format is MP3 (Moving Picture Experts Group Standard 3) and the video podcast format is MP4 (Moving Picture Experts Group Standard 4). Since 2002 and 2005 respectively, educators have developed and popularized the use of blogs and podcasts for both instructional design and instructional activities (Campbell, 2005; King & Gura, 2007; Richardson, 2006; Troutner, 2007 cited in Kim and King, 2011).

The inclusion of podcasts in the educational process is thought to be beneficial for students to produce and present content themselves, thus gaining the ability to express and speak, and making the information they share permanent. "The use of technology can support the shift of the educational dynamic from lecturer-centered to student-centered" (Grisham & Wolsey, 2012). "Being able to be used with any activity, having no time and place limitations, being

portable and useful, allowing repeated listening, allowing to stop and resume from where it was stopped, adjusting the speed and free individual use can be counted among the benefits of audio broadcasts" (Cayhan & Karakaş, 2018, 337). Podcasting is a new technological innovation that combines the Internet with MP3 files that can be downloaded to an iPod or personal computer (Grisham & Wolsey, 2012). The continuing popularity of audio podcasts is due to their convenience for both the creator and the listener (Lee Chan, 2006 cited in Kim & King, 2011). Regarding the appeal and characteristics of podcasts, Campbell (2005) likens it to a theater of the mind that is both compelling and transformative, often far more than anything witnessed visually. He suggests that podcasting at its best can serve as rich content and training in collaborative thinking.

In the study, evaluations were made on how to create learning environments where students can actively participate, produce content and interact through new information and communication technologies and new media tools-both through our own practices and suggestions. Considering today's needs, prospective teachers should develop their competencies in the use of technology in the teaching-learning process as well as other skill areas, and they should have the knowledge and skills to use technology with pedagogy and content knowledge content. Indeed, "The emergence of Web 2.0, which encourages participation, collaboration and interaction on the Internet in the early twenty-first century, has had a profound impact on the World Wide Web becoming increasingly a part of everyday life. The implications for educators have been equally important, with teachers needing to explore how these developments, together with the opportunities provided for students to contribute, share and discuss, can help them to improve teaching and learning in their subjects" (Lyndon, 2012). In the literature, it has been determined that there is a need for researches that will contribute to the development of reading-writing, speaking and listening skills in Turkish and literature courses, especially in foreign language teaching. In this study, which was conducted within the scope of the New Turkish Literature 2 course, Turkish pre-service Turkish teachers were asked to research a Republican period literary figure they wanted to study, and to prepare content by preparing podcasts in at least ten episodes of fifteen minutes each about the literary figure, his/her works and many other information. Within the framework of the determined criteria, they were expected to obtain information not through traditional means, but by researching through the podcast content they prepared, and then to present their knowledge again by speaking and transferring it. Thus, it is thought that the experience of this application by pre-service teachers will contribute to the development of collaborative work, technology use and speaking skills and permanent learning.

It is thought that developing pre-service teachers' perceptions of competence in collaborative work and ICT use in education by using podcast application will contribute to the development of pedagogical and content knowledge of pre-service teachers. It is possible to find studies in the literature on the use of podcasts in educational environments.

In the literature, studies on the use of podcasts in education (Campbell 2005; Richardson 2006; Dlott 2007; Kim 2009a; Borgia 2009; Lonn and Teasley 2009; Lyndon 2012; Kim and King 2011; Guy and Marquis 2016; Bianchi-Pennington 2018; Faughey 2019; Gill 2022) have been conducted in various fields and levels. Podcast applications can also be used to improve listening and speaking skills in courses such as Turkish and literature where verbal communication is predominant. One of the first studies in the literature on the use of podcasts in education is Campbell's (2005) "podcasting in education" study. In this article, he states that podcasts are used at the university level to support learning, reinforce lessons, and attract students' attention more. Campbell (2005) invites educators to think about how they can incorporate podcasts. Studies on the use of podcasts prepared by both teachers and students in grammar (Borgia 2009; Putman and Kingsley 2009), literature (Bianchi-Pennington 2018; Faughey 2019), history (Lyndon 2012) and other fields are important. Again, it has been revealed in the studies conducted in the literature that these practices are carried out at the university level (Guy and Marquis 2016; Gribbins 2007) and at all levels, as well as in primary education (Dlott 2007) and secondary education.

Gill's (2022) study on students' perceptions and experiences of podcasts as a complementary text within the framework of critical media literacy is a new thesis study in the literature. Studies mainly in the field of language teaching (Edirisingh, Rizzi, Ming & Roothwell 2007; Güler 2014; İnce 2015; Koçak 2017; Tahir 2019; Akbaş 2022; Kenger, 2022; Berk 2019; Yorgancı, 2021) are also important.

1. Purpose of the Study

The aim of the study is to examine the attitudes of pre-service teachers who experienced podcasting towards collaborative work in literature course and their perceptions of ICT competence. In addition, pre-service teachers' thoughts about podcasting were also addressed. For this purpose, answers to the following questions were sought:

Turkish pre-service teachers who prepared podcasts in the literature course and worked collaboratively during this application, using technology, getting to know the Republican period literary figures more closely:

1. What are their attitudes towards cooperative learning?

2. What is the level of their perception of competence in using Information Communication Technologies (ICT)?
3. Is there a significant difference between their attitudes towards cooperative learning and their perceptions of competence in using information communication technologies (ICT) according to gender?
4. a) What are your thoughts about enjoying the podcast application?
b) What are your thoughts about the permanence of what you learned during the podcast application process?
c) What are your thoughts about what was done in the preparation process for the podcast application?

2. Method

This section provides information about the purpose, importance, model, study group, data collection and analysis of the study.

3. Research Model

In the study, quantitative and qualitative data collection methods were used together and a mixed method was used to integrate the research results. Concurrent triangulation strategy was used as a mixed research design. The aim is to interpret qualitative and quantitative data collected simultaneously and to provide triangulation. The purpose of using qualitative and quantitative research methods together in the same research is to increase the advantages and decrease the disadvantages of qualitative and quantitative research (Creswell, 2003).

4. Study Group

The research was conducted with thirty-six pre-service teachers from the Faculty of Education who took the New Turkish Literature 2 course and answered the survey questions completely.

5. Data Collection Tools

Quantitative and qualitative data were collected in the study. "Personal Information Form", "Cooperative Learning Attitude Scale" developed by Kiper (2016), "Information and Communication Technologies Competence Perception Scale for Preservice Teachers" developed by Şad and Nalçacı (2015) were used to collect quantitative data. Semi-structured interview form and podcast applications created by pre-service teachers were used to collect qualitative data.

6. Quantitative Data Collection Tools

6.1. Personal Information Form

It was prepared by the researcher for the personal information of the prospective teachers.

6.2. Cooperative Learning Attitude Scale

The "Cooperative Learning Attitude Scale" developed by Kiper (2016) consists of 20 items. Of these 20 items, 11 are positive and 9 are negative. In the evaluation of the positive items, "Strongly Agree" (5), "Agree" (4), "Undecided" (3), "Disagree" (2), "Strongly Disagree" (1), while in the evaluation of the negative items, a five-point Likert-type scale with "Strongly Agree" (1), "Agree" (2), "Undecided" (3), "Disagree" (4), "Strongly Disagree" (5) points was used. Cronbach Alpha coefficient was calculated to reveal the reliability of the scale. Accordingly, the Cronbach Alpha value obtained for the total scale was calculated as 0.824.

6.3. Information and Communication Technologies Competence Perception Scale for Prospective Teachers

Another scale used in the study is the scale developed by Şad and Nalçacı (2015) on Prospective Teachers' Use of Information and Communication Technologies in Education. The scale form is organized in Likert format with 5-point scale ranging from 'I am quite competent' to 'I am quite inadequate'. Cronbach Alpha coefficient of the scale was found to be .964. The scale consists of 30 items.

7. Qualitative Data Collection Tools

7.1. Semi-structured Interview Form

Within the scope of the qualitative dimension of the research, the thoughts of the pre-service teachers who experienced podcast preparation on which aspects of the study they enjoyed (vocalization, getting to know the author, the work closely, permanence of what was learned, etc.) were discussed. For this purpose, a semi-structured interview form consisting of three open-ended questions was prepared by the researcher. In order to ensure the internal validity of these questions, the opinions of field experts who completed their doctorate in the field of Turkish Language Literature Education were taken.

The semi-structured interview questions asked to the pre-service teachers are as follows:

- a) Did you enjoy the podcast application? In which ways?
- b) Did what you learned during the podcast application process become permanent? Can you give information?
- c) Can you give information about the studies you carried out during the preparation process for the podcast application?

8. Data Analysis

The quantitative data obtained in the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as percentage, frequency and arithmetic mean; qualitative data were analyzed using content analysis. With content analysis, it is tried to define the data and to reveal the facts that may be

hidden in the data. The basic process in content analysis is to bring together similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes and to organize and interpret them (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006).

Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were used to check whether the numerical variables were normally distributed.

Descriptive statistics (arithmetic mean and standard deviation) were calculated for the quantitative data obtained in the study in order to determine the attitudes of prospective Turkish language teachers towards cooperative learning and their perception levels of competence in using information and communication technologies (ICT) in education. In order to determine the level of participation from the scores obtained from the scales, the group width value was evaluated using the formula $4/5=.80$. For this purpose; 1.00-1.80 was taken as "very low level"; 1.80-2.60 as "low level"; 2.60-3.40 as "medium level"; 3.40-4.20 as "high level"; 4.20-5 as "very high level".

Content analysis technique was used to analyze the qualitative data. Content analysis attempts to define the data and reveal the facts that may be hidden in the data. The main process in content analysis is to bring together similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes and to interpret them by organizing them (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006). The qualitative data used in the study were obtained from a semi-structured interview form.

9. Podcast Implementation and Planning

In the study, within the scope of the New Turkish Literature 2 course, students were asked to prepare podcasts of at least ten episodes, each episode lasting a maximum of fifteen minutes, on the republican period literary figures they identified themselves. The path followed in the planning of the process and the practices carried out are as follows: Pre-service teachers were informed about the content of the study. Information was given about the relationship between podcast, podcast-literature, podcast-education. Information was given about the names and topics to be covered in the podcast. The names and the number of people to be discussed by the prospective teachers were determined and the topics were distributed to the class. They were provided to do research on articles and books about the literary figures and topics to be covered. Technical information about the realization of the podcast, voice-over, sound editing, etc. information about the related programs was given to the prospective teachers. Sample podcasts were sent to pre-service teachers. Pre-service teachers were encouraged to come together and rehearse. They were provided with episode planning for the podcasts. They were encouraged to prepare draft speeches and rehearse their speeches.

10. Ethics Committee Permission

The data collection tools were submitted to the Ethics Committee of Kütahya Dumlupınar University and it was stated that the study was in compliance with research and publication ethics with the decision presented below:

Board name = Kütahya Dumlupınar University Rectorate, Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee

Date of decision= 15.02.2022

Document number number= E.78513

11. Findings

In this section, findings on the level of pre-service teachers' perceptions of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) competence and their attitudes towards cooperative learning are presented.

11.a. Findings Related to Quantitative Data

Table 1. Normal Distribution Values for Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competency Perception and Cooperative Learning Attitude Scale Total Scores

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Skewness	Kurtosis
	Statistics	sd	p		
Cooperative Learning Scale	0,97	36,00	0,49	0,21	-0,01
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence Perception Scale	0,95	36,00	0,07	0,64	1,45

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In order to determine the analyses to be selected to test the hypotheses, it was checked whether the data were suitable for normal distribution. The significance level obtained from the Shapiro-Wilk normality tests was greater than 0.05, and the kurtosis and skewness values were between ± 2.0 (George & Mallery, 2010) and the values did not deviate excessively from the normal distribution, and parametric tests were performed.

In order to answer the first problem of the study, "What is the level of attitudes of pre-service teachers towards cooperative learning after the podcast application?", the results of the total scores and descriptive statistics of the pre-service teachers are shown in Table 2 and Table 3:

Table 2. Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, Minimum and Maximum Values of Preservice Teachers' Attitudes Towards Cooperative Learning Scale

	N	Min	Maks.	Average	Standard Deviation
Cooperative Learning Scale	36,00	53,00	93,00	69,33	7,20

According to the results in Table 2, the mean score of the pre-service teachers on the cooperative learning attitude scale is 69.33, the standard deviation is 7.20, the highest score is 69 and the lowest score is 53. In order to determine the level of participation from the scores obtained from the scales, the group width value was evaluated using the formula $4/5=0.80$. For this purpose; 1.00-1.80 was taken as "very low level"; 1.80-2.60 as "low level"; 2.60-3.40 as "medium level"; 3.40-4.20 as "high level"; 4.20-5 as "very high level". The result of the division of the total score of the pre-service teachers by the number of items is 3.46 and it can be said that their attitudes towards cooperative learning are at "high" level.

Table 3. Descriptive Results of Cooperative Learning Attitude Levels for Prospective Teachers

	Level	n	%
Cooperative Learning Scale	Undecided	16	44,4
	I agree.	19	52,8
	Absolutely agree	1	2,8

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According to the mean scores obtained from the cooperative learning attitude scale, 52.8% (n:19) of the pre-service teachers were at the level of "agree" and 44.4% (n:16) were at the level of "undecided".

In order to answer the second problem of the study, "What is the level of pre-service teachers' perceptions of competence in using Information Communication Technologies (ICT)?", the total score and descriptive statistics of the pre-service teachers were calculated. The related results are shown in Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4. Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, Minimum and Maximum Values of Preservice Teachers' Perceptions of Competence in Using Information Communication Technologies (ICT)

	N	Min	Maks.	Average	Standard Deviation
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence	36,00	80,00	148,00	109,31	15,57

Perception Scale for Prospective

Teachers

The total scores of the ICT competence perception scale for pre-service teachers were calculated as 109.31 ± 69.33 with a minimum score of 80 and a maximum score of 148. In order to determine the level of participation from the scores obtained from the scales, the group width value was evaluated using the formula $4/5 = .80$. For this purpose; 1.00-1.80 was taken as "very low level"; 1.80-2.60 as "low level"; 2.60-3.40 as "medium level"; 3.40-4.20 as "sufficient level"; 4.20-5 as "quite sufficient level". It can be said that pre-service teachers' perceptions of competence in using Information Communication Technologies (ICT) are at "adequate" level with the result of 3.64 divided by the number of items.

Table 5. Descriptive results of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competency Levels for Prospective Teachers

	Level	n	%
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence Perception Scale for Prospective Teachers	Undecided	12	33,3
	I agree.	20	55,6
	Absolutely agree	4	11,1

100

According to the mean scores obtained from the information and communication technologies (ICT) competence perception scale for pre-service teachers, 55.6% (n:20) of them were at the "agree" level and 33.3% (n:12) were at the "undecided" level.

In order to answer the third problem of the study, "Is there a significant difference between pre-service teachers' attitudes towards cooperative learning and their perceptions of competence in using information communication technologies (ICT) according to gender?", total scores and descriptive statistics were calculated. Related results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Comparison of Cooperative Learning and Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competency Levels by Gender

	Gender	n	$\bar{X} \pm SS$	T	sd	p
Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competence Perception Scale for Prospective Teachers	Male	13	112,00 \pm 17,00	0,78	34,00	0,44
	Woman	23	107,78 \pm 14,87			
Cooperative Learning Scale	Male	13	69,62 \pm 9,87	0,17	34,00	0,86

Woman 23 69,17±5,40

The study sample consisted of 63.9% (n:23) female and 36.1% (n:13) male individuals. As seen in Table 6, there is no statistically significant difference between pre-service teachers' collaborative attitude scores and ICT competency scores according to gender ($p>0.05$).

11. b. Findings related to qualitative data

The findings obtained as a result of analyzing the opinions of pre-service teachers about the podcasts they put forward with the content analysis method are given.

1. The answers to the question "whether they enjoyed the study" were evaluated in six codes. Fifteen pre-service teachers stated that they enjoyed vocalizing in the study, ten pre-service teachers stated that they enjoyed researching about the author/poet and that they had a lot of fun. Four pre-service teachers stated that they enjoyed working collaboratively, and seven pre-service teachers stated that they learned new programs by getting to know the technology more closely. Examples of these students' thoughts are as follows:

Table 7. Did You Enjoy the Podcast Application? Category and Frequency Distributions Related to the Question

<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	101
Without vocalizing, without speaking, and without making his own work		
Those who stated that they enjoy listening to the music	15	
Doing research about the author/poet those who expressed that they enjoyed it	10	
Those who stated that they enjoyed collaborative work with their friends	7	
He said he was more familiar with technology, new programs Those who stated that they gained awareness because they learned	4	

Examples of those who enjoyed the voice-over:

- I enjoyed the voice-over, which was the basis of the podcast assignment, it was a different experience for me. S30
- I enjoyed it. I really enjoy reading poetry and vocalizing texts. S32
- It was a pleasure to talk because it was the first time I realized such an application and I was excited because it was the first time for me, so I did it with enthusiasm. S33

Examples of those who stated that they enjoyed researching about the author/poet:

- I liked to learn a lot of information about the author. S1
- I enjoyed it a lot, especially the research part. S4

Examples of those who stated that they enjoyed collaborative work with their friends:

- We spent time together with my friends. I enjoyed it the most. S5
- Yes, I enjoyed it. I learned a lot of new information about the author, which helped me to get to know him better. S6
- It was fun to learn new information about the person I researched. S11
- The fact that it was in the mood of a conversation rather than doing it individually motivated me more for the assignment. I gained a detailed knowledge about the authors. S19
- Collaborative work is one of the activities I enjoy the most. S32
- It was a lot of fun to work together with my friends. For this reason alone, I think most of the program we did will stay in my mind. S15
- It was good that it was a group assignment. We both took part in a joint work and achieved good things together. S35

Those who stated that they got to know technology more closely and learned new programs:

- At the beginning of this practice, I realized that I was using technology only for social media. We had to work on various programs to record audio and I got a lot of ideas. S3
- I learned a new application in the use of technology and the use of that application, it was really very instructive and enjoyable. S4
- We did a lot of research on the use of technology. Of course I had shortcomings. There were also times when I clicked and felt inadequate about technology. S10
- Since I am good at using technology, I completely undertook this part of the program. I completed it by using different sound editing programs other than Anchor. S20

2. The answers and examples related to the question "What is your opinion about the permanence of what you have learned in this application process?" are as follows:

Table 8. What is your opinion about the permanence of what you learned in the Podcast Application Process? Code and Frequency Distributions Related to the Question

<i>Code</i>	<i>f</i>
Yes	34
No	-
Partly	2

- What I have learned has stuck with me. I can make an impromptu speech about the author I am dealing with now. S3

- With this practice, I had the opportunity to learn more about the work and the author. S7I can't say that it was completely permanent, but of course it has an effect. S9

- I realized that my knowledge was permanent after the study was over. Finding information about the author from many sources, creating texts by editing them and vocalizing them of course made my knowledge permanent. S12

- I made more effort to assimilate the information I researched. Therefore, I think it is permanent S19

- I also learned what I did not know about our poet. It definitely has permanence. S32

- I think that what they learned is permanent because we found all the information we discussed by researching and making efforts, I think that the information that cannot be obtained and learned in this way will be permanent S34

3. Examples of students' statements about the activities carried out during the preparation process for the podcast application:

- We prepared draft speeches and rehearsed speeches, so we had a lot of permanent information about the author. S7

- First of all, I like this podcast app because we don't shoot videos. I was happy that we recorded audio in the podcast. It can be said that it helped me to use my voice correctly. Of course, I read about the topics I will cover, I think the importance of creating a draft for the quality of this application is indisputable. I think the draft is the building block of this application and we have prepared this building block in our own way. Yes, I listened to podcasts from various hosting providers and I already warmed up to this application. Yes, I made preparations in some places until the introduction sentence for each episode. S8

- We gathered information from websites, articles and the poet's books. We prepared the transcripts. We used other podcasts. We planned the episodes before we started podcasting. We divided the topics into episodes and then recorded them. S12

- First of all, we gathered information about the poet. We had two meetings about the content of the ten episodes we were going to shoot and made joint decisions about the process. We also arranged a studio where we would shoot. We contacted people who would help and teach us to record and then edit the recording. When we made the first recording, we adjusted the lengths of the texts we prepared and realized the mistakes in our voiceover. We continued our way by correcting them. We

listened to other podcasts both in terms of content and voiceover. we considered a podcast called "Bookless Literature" still listen to that channel. S13

- We did research about the person we dealt with from many sources, we did readings, we tried to get information about him/her through videos and interviews. First, we created a draft text, then we made edits on it and started vocalizing. We planned the topic we would cover in each episode. We named the episodes according to their topics. At the beginning, we made test recordings and rehearsals. S14

- We listened to other podcasts. We also rehearsed speeches. Of course, before we did this, we prepared an outline, we read works about the person we were dealing with and we made evaluations about adding them to the podcast. We chose the most appropriate one. We practiced vocalization. S17

- First of all, we went through a preparation phase while preparing the podcast. We listened to different podcasts and thought about what we could do. Then we tried to get as much information as we could by doing different researches. After reading different written sources and preparing a draft text, we tried to enrich the product we prepared by turning to different audio sources. Finally, we tried to eliminate our deficiencies by reading before recording the audio. S32

Conclusions And Recommendations

In the study, evaluations were made on how to create learning environments in which students can actively participate, produce content and interact through new information and communication technologies and new media tools, both through our own practices and suggestions. For this purpose, in the research, pre-service teachers were enabled to produce content on Turkish literature literati and their works through podcast application. Considering today's needs, pre-service teachers should develop their competencies in the use of technology in the teaching-learning process as well as other skill areas, and they should have the knowledge and skills to use technology with pedagogy and content knowledge content. As a matter of fact, twenty-first century skills require this. The aim of the study is to examine the attitudes of pre-service teachers who realized the podcast application towards collaborative work in literature course and their perceptions of ICT competence. In addition, pre-service teachers' thoughts about preparing podcasts were also discussed. The findings obtained as a result of the research are that:

1. Pre-service teachers' perceptions of collaborative work towards podcasting are at a "high" level; the mean scores of pre-service teachers' perceptions of ICT competence are at a "sufficient" level; there is no significant difference between their attitudes towards collaborative learning and their perceptions of competence in using information and communication technologies (ICT) according to gender.
2. The findings for the qualitative part are that the pre-service teachers enjoyed the study, their knowledge was reinforced with the preparations they made before the podcast on the subject they dealt with, and this provided permanence. They also stated that speaking and vocalizing, producing content was very satisfying, working with a friend was enjoyable, they learned new things about the use of technology through podcasts and saw their deficiencies. It is thought that the inclusion of podcasts in the educational process will contribute to the students' ability to present the information they have researched by producing content, their ability to express and speak, and the permanence of the information they share.
3. In the literature, studies on the use of podcasts in education have been conducted in various fields and levels. Among these studies, Guy and Marquis (2016) conducted a study on the podcast performance of university students in traditional and flipped classroom environments. They found that students in the flipped classroom performed better than in the traditional style education classroom (cited in Gill, 2022). Among the studies on the use of teacher-produced podcasts for vocabulary teaching in primary and secondary education, Borgia (2009) and Putman and Kingsley (2009) also found that podcasts improved students' vocabulary acquisition. Studies in which students created their own podcasts (Dlott 2007; Bianchi-Pennington 2018; Faughey 2019) are important. Dlott (2007) led elementary school students in a podcast project and used student-made podcasts and blogs for podcast discussions. He concluded that the use of podcasts led to improvements in writing, listening and motivation. Similarly, Faughey (2019) conducted a classroom podcast project that blended in-school and out-of-school literacies in the classroom environment through a literature app about Romeo and Juliet (as cited in Gill, 2022). Görgün (2015) found that teacher-structured out-of-class ICT activities, including podcasting, had positive effects on students' listening skills, intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy in listening.
4. The results of various studies (Stanley 2006; Rosell-Aguilar 2007; Mapuva, Stoltenkamp & Muyengwa 2010) show that podcasting provides learners with a richer and more flexible learning experience and that podcasting is deeply related to constructivism because learners acquire knowledge through active exploration, observation, processing and interpretation. Bianchi-

Pennington (2018) presented a classroom project in which students created a podcast by analyzing literature. Through student-generated podcasts and student-led podcasts, it was stated that students collaborate, make their voices heard and show themselves and contribute to the understanding of classroom topics (see Gill, 2022). The book chapter on the use of blogs and podcasts in history teaching was written by Lyndon (2012). Lyndon (2012) argues that with the emergence of blogs and podcasts, which are easily accessible and user-friendly tools in history classrooms, teachers and teachers. As an example of its use in language teaching, Ducate and Lomicka (2009) used podcasts as a tool to improve pronunciation in their study. Kim (2009a, 2009b) stated that there is a need for more applications in this direction, which reveals the importance of using podcasts and blogs as instructional technology, especially in the education of ESL teacher candidates.

5. Considering the findings obtained from this study and the results of the studies conducted in the literature, it should be stated that podcast applications to be prepared by students and teachers can be included more in the process of education and training. It should be underlined once again that the use of new applications in teacher training and teacher education is of great importance in the realization of studies aimed at helping students access information through research, collaborative work, the use of technology, and the development of verbal communication skills.

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